

OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESS PARAMETERS FOR FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION USING TOOL PATH REVERSING

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Project description

- A novel method to automatically build a finite element (FE) model from a given geometry and process parameters
 - Image recognition techniques are used to analyse the GCode instructions to build a FE model
 - The FE model is used to optimise the process parameters which govern the fused filament fabrication (FFF) manufacturing process
- Simulations were experimentally verified
 - Image recognition techniques are used to analyse the GCode instructions to build a FE model
 - The FE model is used to optimise the process parameters which govern the fused filament fabrication (FFF) manufacturing process
- A genetic algorithm (GA) based optimisation is demonstrated
 - The optimization routine was demonstrated on a simple cube
 - Though a GA based optimization was demonstrated, the simulation platform is built in such a way that any optimisation algorithm can be used
- Customizable and compatible 3rd party tools (and even open source tools)
 - The modular approach of the optimization platform enables the easy replacement of all proprietary software used in this project

Simulation Possibilities

Thermal Simulation

Simulation of temperature variation with time as the thermoplastic material sequentially extruded on to the manufactured part

Mechanical Simulation

The images presented show the stress contours developed in a ISO 527 1A type tensile test specimen with a honeycomb infill when loaded in tension

Simulation flow chart

Results

Validation of simulation with experimental results

Infill density Vs Stiffness
Material: Colorfabb XT

Optimisation results

PARAMETER	OPTIMAL VALUE
INFILL TYPE	Cubic
INFILL DENSITY	85.7%
PERIMETERS	3
TOP AND BOTTOM SOLID LAYERS	1

Optima

Variation of objective and constraint functions function over generations